

Recommended citation: Mahmud, M. N., & Ridgman, T. W. (2018). Interdisciplinary Learning in Engineering Practice. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 297-305). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672546.

Interdisciplinary Learning in Engineering Practice

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Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Continuing EE and Lifelong Learning, Philosophy and Purpose of Engineering Education

Keywords: Skills & Knowledge, Interdisciplinary Knowledge, Engineering Practice, Employability

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 100 years from the Mann Report (1918) [1] to current day IET (2017) [2] there has been criticism of the state of preparedness of newly graduated engineers for their initial engineering practice. Most attention has been paid to the perceived skills gaps but little attention towards the perceived knowledge gaps. These gaps exist because of the necessarily generic nature of university education and the specific requirements of individual job roles. Also the majority of engineering courses are in single disciplines while much of engineering practice is interdisciplinary. This study seeks to understand how students could be better prepared to overcome those knowledge gaps by examining how practicing engineers acquire their interdisciplinary knowledge. It looks at the epistemic practices they engage with, why they choose particular practices, the barriers they encounter, and what are the resulting knowledge outcomes.

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1 BACKGROUND

1.1 Knowledge Acquisition for Early Career Engineers

There is limited research on engineering knowledge; Vincenti (1990) [3] synthesised six categories of engineering design knowledge and Dowling & Hadgraft (2013) [4] developed methodology to identify discipline-based capabilities including the knowledge component. Nonaka (1994) [5] identified an additional challenge in knowledge research where knowledge changes from explicit to tacit and back to explicit, therefore data subjects find it hard to identify what knowledge they have and how they are using it.

Trevelyan (2009) [6] quantifies how early career engineers spend their time overcoming the capability gaps from their engineering education and suggests that a better model of engineering practice is required to help design more effective engineering education. The gap has been confirmed in other studies such as Ridgman and Liu (2014) [7] in China and Ridgman (2013) [8] for India. The importance of understanding how to acquire interdisciplinary knowledge is illustrated by Dixon (2015) [9] that shows that the coherence between degree title and area of practice of employment is between 15% and 60%.

1.2 Challenges for Engineering Education

The default engineering education paradigm is that students are taught useful engineering knowledge that they 'apply' in practice. This has to be defended against criticism from employers that University teaches out of date, single discipline material at a low technical level. Early career engineers find they have to work hard to cover the gap between what they have been taught and the knowledge needed to do their jobs. While these criticisms/arguments are longstanding as the employability agenda develops, and the view of the student as a consumer is developing, they will come under much greater scrutiny.

If the specific knowledge that any particular graduating engineer will need at the start of their career is not predictable then educators need to focus on helping students understand and improve their personal knowledge acquisition skills. The knowledge acquisition process consists of several components - realising what needs to be known, finding knowledge and deciding whether and how to use it. This research looks at the final stage of that process.

2 RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The research started with a single case that was analysed to produce a simple model. The model was then evaluated using a range of methods to compare its variables with a range of issues identified from the literature. This resulted in a refined model which was then tested on two further cases chosen using the criteria of 'most-likely' and 'least-likely scenarios'.

2.1 Initial Case Selection

To be able to clearly identify the "new" knowledge acquired and avoid the tacit/explicit issues it was decided to research practicing engineers carrying out interdisciplinary life science projects. The case selected was based on a team of engineers and a biochemist who worked on a project at a leading biotech company to increase the production of a therapeutic hormone. To achieve a successful outcome to the project the engineers needed to acquire life science knowledge of 'craft' processes and convert them to engineering knowledge and deliver a successful robotic solution. Two engineers and one biochemist were chosen as research subjects.

2.2 Analysis Methods

The research analysis was designed to adhere to the five principles of data analysis according to the critical realism philosophy outlined by Wynn and Williams (2012) [10]. These are: explication of events, explication of structure and content, reproduction of mechanisms, empirical corroboration and triangulation of methods. The reliance on a single exploratory case calls for a range of coding techniques and action coding, causation coding and pattern coding were carried out as suggested by Saldaña (2012) [11]. Since the research was carried out using a social material perspective this suggested the use of an actor network theory analytical framework, Callon (1986) [12]. The typology and the identification of inferences and their relationships were derived using the techniques outlined in the non-statistical analysis of a small number of instances, George and Bennett (2005) [13].

Procedure	Method	Outcome
Coding the interview data	Coding Techniques	Codes and conceptual categories
Framing and re-describing key aspects	Actor Network Theory Framework	Patterns of Causal Relationships
Characterising Causal Patterns	Typology	Types of causal relationships
Generating causal inferences	Comparative Method	Causal inferences
Evaluating causal inferences	Congruence Method	Established and unresolved causal relationships
Validating causal relationships	Casual Process Tracing Methodology	Tentative Theoretical framework
Refining and generalising theoretical framework	Cross Case analysis	Proposed Theoretical Framework

Table 1. Summary of Research Methods

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Simple Model

The first stages of the analysis used action codes and causation codes from the interview transcripts to develop conceptual categories for the actions engineers took to develop their knowledge (epistemic practices) and the outcomes of those actions (knowledge outcomes).

3.1.1 Epistemic Practices

Initially three epistemic practices were identified

CEP - Consultational Epistemic Practice: A set of related activities taken to gain further understanding about the life science knowledge they encountered. For example the life scientist have to explain why they need to heat a sample to a given temperature in a way that is understandable both in a life science and an engineering context.

TEP - Translational Epistemic Practice: A set of related activities taken on the content and forms of the life science knowledge in order to arrive at the knowledge contents and forms that can be used to develop solutions – For examples the life scientist may regularly stir something but to useful in the project the ‘stirring’ has to be converted into a set of engineering parameters such as vessel size, paddle speed, fluid shear forces, duration, etc.

EEP - Evidential Epistemic Practice: A set of related activities taken to gain and show confirmation of the usefulness of the different contents and forms of knowledge. For example in order to fit some parameters to a life science craft activity it may be necessary to carry out some experiments.

3.1.2 Knowledge Outcomes

Adoption – Able to understand, appreciate and reuse the relevant knowledge while retaining the content and meaning. This was the case when the life science knowledge fitted easily into the physical science knowledge of engineering and could be considered as any other engineering rule.

Translation – Able to develop and use knowledge whose terms and forms usefully differ from, but correspond to, those used in, or provided by, the other discipline. In this case the life science knowledge can be translated into an engineering equivalent where the engineering rules for the equivalent are satisfactory for the project context.

Avoidance – Able to avoid pursuing the learning and using the knowledge contents and forms that do not contribute to the successful development of the solution. In this outcome the life science knowledge is not immediately relevant to the project and therefore doesn't need to be considered further.

Addition – Able to add knowledge that is new to the collaborators from other disciplines and evidently useful for improving their practices. In this case through discussion with the engineers the life scientist develop a new understanding of how their process works.

3.1.3 Preliminary Model from Case Study 1

Having identified practices and outcomes the next stage of the model development is to understand how they are linked together. From the transcripts it is possible to identify action codes where a practice is linked to a satisfactory knowledge outcome and 'predicament' codes where the outcome of a practice is not satisfactory and therefore a different practice is considered. This resulted in the initial model shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Initial model

3.2 Developing the Model

The model above is very simple but does not help in understanding why engineers were able to undertake those practices and be successful in overcoming the predicaments rather than abandoning their learning prematurely.

3.2.1 Modes of Epistemic Engagement

Actor Network Theory (ANT) was used to identify three modes of epistemic engagement and three barriers to accepting knowledge.

Perspectival Mode – This occurs in the ‘problematization’ moment in ANT theory where different actors are attempting to render themselves indispensable to others by framing the nature of the problem according to what they know. By looking at the life scientist perspective they were able to recognise social-material elements on which they could consult and interact further. They could adopt the knowledge, if it was useful, or attempt to translate it into engineering terms.

Justificational Mode – In ANT’s ‘moment of enrolment’ the actors try to overcome their disagreements by justifying their positions. This justification mode is where the engineers seek justification for seemingly ambiguous knowledge.

Complemental Mode – This also occurs in the ‘moment of enrolment’ and is where engineers think about improvements that could be made to their understanding by developing new knowledge.

3.2.2 Evaluating Causal Inferences

In the evaluation of casual inferences congruence analysis is used to determine if there might be other variables suggest by literature that could be influencing the outcomes. Three of these were identified as being an important addition to the model.

Communication Barrier – During the consultation phase a lack of understanding of the life science perspective was a causal factor in the engineers’ decision to attempt to make a translation into an engineering paradigm.

Contradictory Barrier – Professional practices exhibit ‘discordant practices’ where espoused values and enacted practices differ. When faced with a perception that what the life scientist said, and what they did, differed the engineers would seek additional evidence to resolve the contradiction.

Contributory Barrier – Although the engineers may have developed an understanding in engineering terms of a project it could be difficult to persuade the life scientists of this without producing ‘hard’ evidence. This became a driver of engagement in EEP.

3.3 Refinements from Supporting Case Studies

3.3.1 Nature of Case Studies

The second case study interviewed 3 engineers from different engineering disciplines who had been involved in a project to develop an automated micro-scale bioreactor. This required knowledge development from the whole team because the engineers were unfamiliar with the biological processes and the life scientists had never used, or see, any representation of ‘scale down’ from lab equipment to micro-bioreactors.

The third case study interviewed two engineers who were developing a device to test lung function. The engineers needed to gain medical knowledge of lung function and diagnosis but also the safety and usability requirements for hospital equipment.

3.3.2 Additional Variables from the Cross Case Analysis

CPEP - Comparative Epistemic Practice. Comparing knowledge suggested or practiced by others against a set of criteria that are underpinned by the engineers' prior knowledge. For example the design engineer compared the requirements for micro-bioreactor with the existing knowledge of conventional scale bioreactors.

Implication Barrier – This occurred when the life scientists were unclear of the implications of the engineering solution. For example the life scientists did not know how cells might behave when subjected to the micro-reaction process. To understand this some form of experimentation was required. This led to an additional engagement mode, the implication mode, to determine whether the knowledge encountered has implications for the solution under development.

A further refinement to the model was to better understand that the linkage between the consultational epistemic practice and knowledge adoption was based on analogous perception. Faced with the new knowledge if the engineers thought there was a good analogy to their existing understanding and if they did not perceive any discordant practice or ambiguity they were satisfied that they could adopt the knowledge.

3.4 Final Model

These findings have been brought together in a generalised theoretical framework (Fig 2). The framework has been developed in the context of a team of interdisciplinary engineers working with life scientists to produce an engineered product. The engineers respond to knowledge suggestions from their life science collaborators based on their perception of whether they have sufficient knowledge to engage with the suggestion. Then they either feel confident in engaging in consultation or seek an engineering analogy as a start point in developing their understanding.

They can then accept the lifescience knowledge and add it to their own knowledge base, translate it from a life science perspective into an engineering perspective or carry out some experimentation to validate the knowledge. This leads to a range of outcomes of adopting the knowledge as expressed by life scientists, translated engineering knowledge, avoiding the knowledge because it is not perceived as useful for the project. The final outcome is creating new knowledge by combining engineering and life science knowledge.

Fig. 2. Generalised Theoretical Framework

4 INSIGHTS FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION

As discussed earlier the gap between engineering as taught at Universities and as practiced in industry has been extensively researched over many years. Changes, such as project based learning, to narrow the gap being limited and very slow to permeate through the sector.

Some of the pressures on the sector, driven by student consumerism, 'teach to the test', collective disengagement etc., are likely to widen the gap by producing highly credentialed students with limited ability to practice and limited intellectual development. Using Perry's 9 stage framework of intellectual development Felder and Brent (2004) [14] discovered that engineering students were generally between 2.5 and 3.5 with less than a third making it to level 5. As this level of intellectual development students are only equipped to deal with well-defined problems and complete data as opposed to the uncertainty and ambiguity that characterises day-to-day engineering problem solving.

This initial work is very exploratory but has provided a framework to help students deal with the challenges of understanding the learning process they will need to adopt early in their career.

4.1 Development of Professional Identity

More work has to be done to help students develop their identity as engineers to smooth their transition from new graduate to early career engineers. While plugging the gap in practice will take a long time with the slow rate of change in engineering education at least being able to explain the issue will help remove discontent. A framework is needed to explain how learning takes place in practice and how to manage the transition from discipline based study to inter-disciplinary project work. Interdisciplinary work has to be founded on solid disciplinary competence but most projects and products are realised by interdisciplinary

teams. Much of the work on helping students think about these transitions has focussed on developing team and other interpersonal skills there is little support for them to either understand that they will have to increase their level of intellectual development and learn how to manage their own knowledge acquisition.

4.2 Developing Pedagogic Strategies

The first step in developing strategies to improve personal knowledge acquisition is to introduce students to interdisciplinary projects and ambiguous information. However while many courses have adopted projects in some form the assessment of knowledge gained by the students or, even better, the students' ability to self assess the knowledge acquired is very limited. Students tend to focus on the project outcome, with some limited reflection of the team/transferrable skills development.

The first stages would be to combine knowledge acquisition development with existing teaching of critical thinking and project reflection journals enabling the students to identify what knowledge they identified for the project, the barriers they faced in understanding it, how they tested its applicability and its relevance. Once some expertise had been developed in this mode of teaching it could be introduced earlier in the curriculum particularly in a flipped classroom methodology since both flipped class and engineering projects are both aimed at developing self directed learning.

5 CONCLUSIONS

To advance the knowledge of our students, to help them develop their professional identities as engineers and to reduce the stress of their early career learning we need to help them understand how to use ambiguous knowledge in complex problem solving. This involves developing a personal knowledge acquisition competence that includes how to find knowledge, evaluate it for its usefulness to the problem in hand, recognise, and overcome the barriers to use and test when necessary. In a world where knowledge is available at a press of a key the competitive advantage lies in understand when, where and whether to use it. The exploratory research has developed a preliminary framework to help understand the knowledge acquisition process.

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